

REPORTING OF VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN MAINSTREAM MEDIA AND ITS SUBSEQUENT EFFECT IN FORMULATING PUBLIC OPINION FOR TOUGHER PUNISHMENTS (CASE STUDY- HYDERABAD RAPE CASE 2019)

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ABSTRACT

Media in contemporary world is de facto source of news regarding crime taking place in society, its nature, severity and most importantly its perpetrators. Reporters and anchors communicate to public every minute detail of the crime generating not only public interest but also sympathy for victim and detest for criminal. It's been observed that crimes of heinous nature are generally more highlighted by media and one taking part regularly. Also reports have shown that mostly rape or other sort of violence against women (VAW) is viewed as result of incompetence of government, police and that of justice system rather than of conditions in society as a whole . There are trenchant talk of harder punishments and vindictiveness but rarely of criminal reforms or societal reforms. In this scenario public isn't left with much choice but to perceive criminal as threat to society and in want of tougher punishment for them. In the given study we have taken variable such as economic status, education level, gender, exposure to both new and conventional media etc. to decode public support for tougher punishments in violence against women and its dependence on coverage of the event by media (new and conventional).

One of the objectives of the study is also to study is there's difference in perception of crimes and punishment among audiences of new and conventional media?

Keywords: Media Coverage, Public Opinion, Social Awareness, Violence Against Women.

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Bu makaleye atf yapmak için / Cite this article: Binjola H, Bisht D, Patel K. (2024). Reporting of Violence Against Women in Mainstream Media and Its Subsequent Effect in Formulating Public Opinion for Tougher Punishments. *The Journal of World Women Studies*, 9(1), 20-39. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14585903>

INTRODUCTION

Media today is omnipresent. With its overarching presence in our lives, from televisions to smartphones to FM bursting in cars, persistent in delivering its message. Through this ever-working channel journalist formulate citizen's opinion regarding crime, criminals and punishments. Media questions government, party in power, police, lawyers, activists or even commoners. Not enough attention has been given to role of media how media has developed a monopoly over conveying of news in regards to VAW (violence against women) and how change in coverage strategies can actually bring forth a positive change. Media hardly runs any story on women safety or criminal reforms but thrives on insecurities of public when crime of heinous nature take place. Governments too are not ready to speak against public sentiments and more than ever are ready to comply with public mandate.

When incidents like Hyderabad rape case takes place government instead of bringing swift justice through existing judicial system more often than not give inflammatory remarks in order to mollify public. Infact in recent times crime and tougher punishment for crimes are an important part of politician's rhetoric with xenophobic and religious bigoted comments taking place side by side. Much of reporting is done to drive on public anger and very less on actual reasons and solutions of the problem. Journalists still after knowing they are the opinion leaders of society are quite negligent and engage in media trials. People with exposure to media round the clock are more likely to ask for tougher punishment including capital punishment then the one who are not.

Violence Against Women in India

Different IPC sections for crime against women in India (Bajaj, n.d.)

1. Rape (Sec 376 IPC);
2. Kidnapping and abduction for different purposes (Sec 363-373 IPC) (within which the crimes pertaining to women and girls only are included in our analysis here);
- 2
3. Homicide for dowry, dowry deaths or attempts to commit such crimes (Sec 302/304B IPC);
4. Torture, both mental and physical (Sec 498-A IPC);
5. Molestation (Sec 354 IPC);
6. Sexual harassment (Sec 509 IPC) (referred to as 'eve-teasing' in the past);
- 3 and
7. Importation of girls (up to 21 years of age, Sec 366-B IPC).

Following is the ratio of VAM (violence against women) in India according to data provided by UN

Prevalence Data on Different Forms of Violence against Women: (unwomen.org, n.d.) Lifetime Physical and/or Sexual Intimate Partner Violence: 28.8 %

- Physical and/or Sexual Intimate Partner Violence in the last 12 months: 22%
- Lifetime Non-Partner Sexual Violence: Official National Statistics Not Available
- Child Marriage: 27.3 %

India's performance in Gender Parity Indexes

Gender Equality Indexes: (UNDP, 2020)

- Gender Inequality Index Rank: 125
- Global Gender Gap Index Rank: 87

Following is the more elaborate and comprehensible data available on violence against women in India through National Family Health Survey (NHFS-4)

According to the survey, 27 per cent of women have experienced physical violence since the age 15 in India. This experience of physical violence among women is more common in rural areas than among women in urban areas. Domestic violence cases, where women reported physical abuse in rural and urban areas, were at 29 per cent and 23 percent, respectively.

The survey reported that among married women who have experienced physical violence since the age of 15, 83 per cent reported their present husbands as perpetrators of the violence. However, for women who are not married, the experience of physical violence stems from the most common perpetrators, which includes mothers or step-mothers (56%), fathers or step-fathers (33%), sisters or brothers (27%), and teachers (15%).

However, the most worrying part of the spousal-violence is that almost every third married women, who has experienced spousal violence, reported experiencing physical injuries, including eight per cent who have had eye injuries, sprains, dislocations, or burns and six per cent who have had deep wounds, broken bones, broken teeth, or any other serious injury. Yet, only 14 per cent of women who experienced this violence sought help to stop it.

Data from the survey shows women in India between the ages of 40 to 49 were most supportive of domestic violence, with 54.8% in agreement. The percentage justifying abuse is marginally lesser.

Among younger women. 47.7% of girls between the age of 15 and 19 agreed with violence by husbands

This marginal difference in attitudes of women towards domestic violence is also visible in urban and rural areas. While 54.4% of rural women surveyed across the country agreed with domestic abuse, only 46.8% of urban women supported such violence.

Sexual Violence (Chauhan, 2019)

6% of women in India and reported to having experienced sexual violence in their lifetime.

Among married women who were victims of sexual violence, over 83% reported their present husband and 9% report a former husband as the perpetrators.

The form of sexual violence most commonly reported by women was that their husband used physical force to have sexual intercourse when they did not want to (5.4%). About 4% reported that their husband forced them with threats or in other ways to perform sexual acts they did not want to, and 3% reported that their husband forced them to perform other sexual acts they did not want to.

Husbands and wives being out of the purview of rape laws enables men to 'prey' on women in the security of her home. These statistics give a clear indication of the kind of sexual harassment and violence young girls and women face in India.

The scenario for unmarried women is no different. The survey report highlighted that most common perpetrators of sexual violence on unmarried women were other relatives (27%), followed by a current or former boyfriend (18%), their own friend or acquaintance (17%) and a family friend (11%).

Sexual violence is most often committed by individuals with whom women have an intimate relationship. Physical violence and sexual violence may not occur in isolation; rather, women may experience a combination of different types of violence," the survey report said.

The report stated that experience of domestic violence, including physical and sexual violence decreases sharply with schooling and education.

By schooling, the percentage of women who report physical violence declined from 38 per cent among women with no schooling to 16 per cent among women with 12 or more years of formal education.

Similarly, experience of sexual violence decreases sharply with schooling from eight per cent among women with no schooling to three per cent among women with 12 or more years of schooling.

Femicide

Femicide is the classical clash between Patriarchy and Femininity. "Patriarchy is based on a masculine/warrior ideal. It promotes ideals such as violence, aggression, domination, control, emotional reserve and sexual potency for men. These ideas dangerously get attributed to a „natural“ form of masculinity that all men supposedly possess

Reporting of Violence Against Women in Media

In her study done on Violence against Women: Media (Miss- Representations of Femicide (2003) Sabrina Denney Bull tacitly explains the factors that lead to Femicide 'and how the media, quite ineptly, downplay even distort the facts related to VAW & Femicide.

Wetschanow (2003), Gupta (1999), O'Connor (2002), Caputi et al. (1992) has other notable works on similar issues. According to their study it has been found out that on many instances' media fail to give prominence to news associated to crimes and other violent acts perpetrated on women. The media are blamed of marginalizing, distorting, fabricating and downplaying news when it comes to reporting VAW & Femicide '.

Reporting of Violence Against Women in Indian Media

The following is the study related to reporting of crimes against women in mainstream Indian newspapers by Amanda Gilbertson, Niharika Pandit. (Amanda Gilbertson, 2019)

The research involved gathering all articles on violence against women in four newspapers, the two most widely read English newspapers—Times of India (ToI) and Hindustan Times—and the two most widely read Hindi language newspapers—Dainik Jagran and Hindustan—over two months in mid-2017.

A total of 725 English articles and 804 Hindi articles were collected and analyzed. We found that many common problems in reporting on VAWG in the media were not highly prevalent in our study—victim-blaming, suggesting that victims lie, and exonerating the perpetrator, for example.

The most striking issues in the reporting related to a very high proportion of incident-based reporting and almost no reporting on VAWG as a systemic social problem.

Some interesting observations on the reports on domestic violence are: a lack of reporting, a failure to name domestic violence when it was reported, and a tendency to provide explanations for the violence that could perpetuate “she asked for it” stereotypes.

Differences were also evident between Hindi and English newspapers, with Hindi papers tending to use more emotive language that was at times sensationalist.

Hyderabad Rape Case Timeline

In November 2019, the gang rape and murder of a 26-year-old veterinary specialist in Shamshabad, near Hyderabad, sent shock wave across India. Her body was found in Shadnagar.

In November 2019, the gang rape and murder of a 26-year-old veterinary specialist in Shamshabad, near Hyderabad, sent shock across India. Her body was found in Shadnagar on 28 November 2019, the day after she was killed. Four suspects were captured and, as indicated by the Cyberabad Metropolitan Police, admitted to having assaulted and murdered the doctor.

The Telangana Police Department stated that victim had stopped her scooter near toll booth, which grabbed the eye of two lorry drivers and their colleagues. As indicated by police, they deflated her tyre, claimed to support her, and drove her into close by brambles, where they assaulted and smothered her. At that point they purportedly stacked her death body onto a lorry and dropped it on the side of the road.

The police captured four men dependent on the proof accumulated from CCTV cameras and from the victim's cell phone. The accused were taken into legal guardianship at Cherlapally Central Jail for fourteen days.

The Telangana's Chief Minister Chandrasekhar Rao requested the arrangement of a most optimized plan of fast-track court to attempt the accused for their supposed wrongdoings. The assault and murder inspired shock in a many part of the nation.

The Minister of Home Affairs Amit shah criticized Telangana Police and expressed that the administration meant to change the Indian Penal Code and Code of Criminal Procedure to present laws for snappier discipline by quick track courts.

Every one of the four charged were killed in police encounter on 6 December 2019, under an extension on Bangalore Hyderabad national parkway, while they were in police authority.

As indicated by the police, the suspects were taken to the area for a reconstruction of the wrongdoing scene, where two of them purportedly grabbed weapons and assaulted the police. In the resulting shootout, each of the four suspects were shot dead. Some blamed the police of extrajudicial execution, while thousands for individuals commended the men's demises

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Literature Review

In any culture, the media is central to the superstructure. (Patel, AN ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF PERSONAL COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON PUBLIC POLICY MAKING PROCESS IN INDIA, 2014) Media motivating public for harder punishment and Get-Tough narrative. Scholars tend to agree that the majority of the public's knowledge about crime and the criminal justice system come from the consumption of such a media-rich diet. As a result, it is essential to understand how the media influences public attitudes, particularly on the criminal justice system's ultimate punishment—the death penalty. For the vast majority of people living in the western world, the primary source of information about crime (both locally and globally) appears to be the mass media (Daly, 1995; Knowles 1982; Skogan & Maxfield, 1981).

Moreover, given their ubiquity, the mass media have the potential to play an integral role in the construction of most people's crime reality (Barlow, Barlow, & Chiricos, 1995): A significant role of the media is to track and educate human society about all the developments in the world (Patel, AN ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF PERSONAL COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON PUBLIC POLICY MAKING PROCESS IN INDIA, 2014). A reality often not mirrored in official crime statistics (Finkel & Groscup, 1997). However, in constructing social, political, and economic realities, the media rarely disclose all of the relevant or material facts (Brownstein, 1991). Instead, the media engage in the selective use of information that consistently produces a less than objective representation of reality (Chermak, 1994; Hans, 1990) Roberts & Doob, 1984, 1990). And human suffering that crime inflicts can, it is not surprising that the polls also report sometimes generate a fear so pervasive and intense that crime has replaced issues such as economic that the public is left feeling powerless. Politicians' policy and unemployment as the 'most important' use this fear to considerable advantage Policies such problem people now face (Flanagan, 1996).

The most cited reasons are, that people are tired of crimes and that they want to "get tough" on criminals. Popular debates and discussions suggest four main reasons why people support capital punishment. They included: that capital punishment deters other. Criminals by setting up an example that the same will happen to them if they commit crimes; that it ensures that convicted serious criminals will never repeat their crimes; that it saves the taxpayer the cost of keeping a person in prison for life; and, that it is a just and deserved punishment for anyone who commits a serious crime (Vidmar, 1974).

The growth of the media was traced through technological progress in the form of chronological development and its effect on social reform. (Patel, Impact of Advancements in Technological Aids in Communication Media in Bringing About Social Reformation, 2018) Scholars in the area of social control have long posited a relationship between media, popular culture, and perceptions of punishment, including punitive attitudes and support for capital punishment (Demker, Towns, Duus-Otterstrom, & Sebring, 2008; Oliver & Armstrong, 2005; Rosenberger & Callanan, 2011; Sotirovic, 2001. Other surveys have also found that deterrence is often the most cited reason for supporting harsh sanctions and the death penalty (Maguire and Pastore, 1995; Thomas, 1977; Vidmar, 1974).

The literature strongly suggests that the general public is both uninformed about the death penalty and unaware of whether it achieves its desired outcomes. Moreover, the literature suggests that the death penalty may in some cases actually increase the violent crime rate because of the brutalization effect (Amsterdam, 1982; Bailey, 1983; Bowers, 1984; Bowers & Pierce, 1980; Knorr, 1979; Radelet & Akers, 1996). The present trend towards law-and-order politics Justification for these and other harsh sentences emerged at a time when governments, governing practices is found in the popular rationale of a weakened by unstable economies, have embraced punitive public 'fed up' with crime and the rhetoric of 'get tough on crime' (Braithwaite, increasingly dissatisfied with the criminal justice system 1999).

The literature strongly suggests that the general public is both uninformed about the death penalty and unaware of whether it achieves its desired outcomes (Bohm, 1987, 1989, 1998; Bohm, Clark, & Aveni, 1990, 1991; Bohm, Vogel, & Maisto, 1993; Ellsworth & Ross 1983; Firment & Geiselman, 1997; Sarat & Vidmar, 1976; Vidmar & Dittenhoffer, 1981; Wright, Bohm, & Jamieson, 1995).

A Gallup poll reported that 71% of those polled supported the death penalty (Zeisel & Gallup, 1989). However, when asked if they could be shown convincingly that the death penalty had no deterrent effect on murder, support fell to 55%. Moreover, if they could be shown convincingly that the death penalty had no deterrent effect and life without parole was available as a sanction, only 43% indicated

support for the death penalty. Instead, most crime is attributed to small, easily identifiable groups within the community — an attribution that racial and minority groups claim is the basis for discrimination at the hands of the criminal justice system (e.g., Angeli, 1997).

A regular platform in the United States, law-and order are an ideology with a proven track record in that country. The liberal, anti-death penalty stand of the Democratic Party was no match for the ‘fear of crime’ platform adopted by the Republicans in the 1988 United States Presidential race; the Democrats were beaten soundly at the polls. Similarly, New York Mayor Giuliani remained in office for over a decade on the strength of his law-and-order approach to politics (Tonry, 1999).

The desire for crime control seems to have permeated the American psyche. It was the driving force behind the introduction of mandatory prison terms and three strikes legislation (Cullen, Gilbert, & Cullen, 1983; Diamond, 1989; Flanagan, McGarrell, & Brown, 1985; Goodstein & Hephburn, 1986; Tonry, 1999) and has played a major role in the passing of what some consider are harsh and repressive sex offender registration and notification laws that followed the deaths of Megan Kanka and Polly Klaas (Tonry, 1999).

Moreover, riding on the crest of public concern about crime, it legitimised the perception of this issue as one to which politicians could offer a ‘solution’. Similarly, public dissatisfaction with ostensibly rising crime rates, particularly with respect to youth crime, was a significant factor in the passing of mandatory prison legislation in Western Australia and the Northern Territory (Morgan, 1999; Yeats, 1997; Zdenkowski, 1999).

Sentencing, it has been argued, represents the community’s response to those who violate the law and should, therefore, reflect the prevailing social, cultural, and moral norms within that community (Robinson & Darley, 1995). In some circumstances, upholding this philosophy might prove to be problematic. For example, if public opinion is an artificial construction, and therefore not a true reflection of community attitudes, or if the judiciary relies on the public vote to remain in office (as in the United States), sentencing may well reflect misconstrued public opinion rather than the underlying intention of the sentencing law.

On the other hand, the ignoring of public opinion can be equally problematic, as people tend to lose confidence in the criminal justice system when their views are ignored. Such a loss of confidence has been associated with a greater tolerance for vigilante groups (Robinson & Darley, 1995) and an increased tendency for jury members to act in ways that nullify the law (Finkel, 1995).

In recent years, both Garland (2001) and Simon (2007) argue that several significant historical changes have resulted in a culture of fear that has heightened the public’s sensitivity to risk and led to support for increasingly punitive policies. A more specified version of Gebner and the Cultural Indicators Project’s (Gerbner et al., 1977) ‘cultivation hypothesis’ posits that both audience characteristics and the specific content (media form/channel and genre of the content) consumed by the audience influence the relationship between media and fear of crime. In line with this argument, Baumgartner, DeBoef and Boydstury (2008), in the book *The Decline of the Death Penalty and the Discovery of Innocence*, suggest that the news media’s recent focus on innocence cases has led to reduced support of the death penalty on the grounds of fairness. In the research conducted by Demker, Towns, Duus-Otterstrom, and Sebring (2008) in Sweden.

Demker et al. found a correlation between tabloid consumption and punitive, in which regular tabloid readers were more clearly in favour of introducing the death penalty in Sweden than no tabloid readers or those who seldom read tabloids. This was particularly true among males (Demker et al., 2008). Holbert, Shah, and Kwak (2004) studied three genres of crime-related television viewing, including police-reality shows, television news, and crime dramas, and found that all three types of television viewing correlate to sentiments in favour of capital punishment. Research indicates that the majority of public knowledge about crime and justice is derived from the media (Roberts and Doob, 1990; Surette, 1998).

Therefore, it is imperative to examine the effects that the mass media have on attitudes toward crime and justice. In an early study, Gerbner et al (1980) hypothesized that heavy viewing of television violence leads to fear rather than aggression. In a review of the research, Heath and Gilbert (1996) find that the relationship between media presentations and crime is dependent on characteristics of the message and the audience. Presentation of large amounts of local crime news engenders increased fear among the larger public, (Brillon, 1987; Sheley and Ashkins, 1981).

While the presentation of large amounts of non-local crime news has the opposite effect by making the local viewers feel safe in comparison to other areas (Liska and Baccaglini, 1990). In addition Chiricos et al (2000) finds that local and national news are related to fear of crime. The effect of local news on fear of crime is stronger for residents in high crime areas and those who experienced victimization. Liska and Baccaglini (1990) find that media influence was strongest for females, whites and the elderly, which are segments of the population least likely to be victimized.

In another study, Chiricos et al (1997) find that the frequency of watching television news and listening to the news on the radio is significantly related to fear. Their research indicates that television news consumption is significantly related to fear only for white females between the ages of 30 and 44. This is similar to other findings that suggest that watching crime on television has a greater effect for women and whites, who have low victim risk compared to males and non-whites (Gerbner et al., 1980). We have moved, in short, from a time in which punishment and prison were unfashionable to a time in which punishment dominates policy discussions and the prison is embraced as the linchpin of the nation's response to crime. But why has this striking shift occurred? The sources of this transformation in thinking and policy are complex (Beckett 1997), but a commonsense, parsimonious explanation for harsher penalties is frequently offered: punitive policies simply reflect what the public wants. Fed up with intractable crime rates-fed up with coddled offenders victimizing them, people they know, and people they hear about- citizens collectively have made the rational assessment that more offenders should be locked up for longer periods (cf. Beckett 1997; Dilulio 1997).

In this scenario, then, the movement to get tough on crime is an instance of "democracy at work"-of politicians implementing the harsh sanctions demanded by their constituents (Scheingold 1984; Cullen, Clark, and Wozniak 1985; Beckett 1997). This view rests on the assumption that citizens do, in fact, desire a correctional system that does little else than inflict as much punishment as possible. It is noteworthy that commentators make this precise claim; after all, do not public opinion polls demonstrate convincingly that Americans wish to get tough with crime?

Significance of the Study

The media shapes public understanding of violence against women and girls, but until now there has been no systematic review of reporting on violence against women and girls in Indian media and its effect on the perception of crime and its perpetrators by public. Beyond few exceptions, newspaper readers are subjected to a steady stream of often excessively detailed and sometimes sensationalist stories in which incidents appear isolated rather than part of a systemic social issue. Public opinion is subject to both random and systematic errors. For this reason, it is important that periodic assessments of the public's attitudes towards crime and justice be undertaken. Doing so helps to provide an historical record of changes in the public's thinking as it relates to these issues. "Get tough" control policies in the United States are often portrayed as the reflection of the public's will: Americans are punitive and want offenders locked up.

Research from the past decade both reinforces and challenges this assessment. The public clearly accepts, if not prefers, a range of punitive policies (e.g., capital punishment, three-strikes-and you're-out laws, imprisonment). But support for get-tough policies is 'mushy'.

In midst of all this Hyderabad rap case came as a reality test. Though initially mainstream media brushed apart the incident, it gained a lot of clout in social media. Public rage towards the incident and the resentment of not being heard created a lot of online tension. After ignoring it for a while mainstream news channels and newspaper started reporting over the incident.

Anchors shouted for justice from their studios and a lot of coverage was given to politicians asking for quick and hard justice. Actress turned MP Jaya Bachchan demanded to hang rapists publically which got lot of attention in media. Overall there was a lot of pressure upon TRS government to bring criminals to justice. Though a fast-track court was established and accused were arrested quickly public rage was nowhere near the end.

The end to whole episode came with supposedly encounter of accused by the Telangana police. There was already a great desire for an encounter among public as similar act has taken place in Wrangle in 2008 and VC Sajjanar was involved in encounter that time too. As expected, act of encounter was greatly appreciated and applauded by public. Though while act might have brought justice to Disha (pseudo name of victim) the greater change in society is nowhere to be seen. Hashtags were trending till the week afterwards praising Hyderabad model as ideal form of justice.

Objective

1. Researchers wanted to test the amount of exposure in public to New (Social Media) and Conventional media (Radio, Television, Newspaper) in engagement with news in relation with sexual violence. Engagement to be studied through retweets, comments, like/dislike on the news related to given subject matter (Hyderabad Rape Case)

2. Researcher wanted to find if my sample engages with content, he/she is fed through New Media. Engagement through content can be studied through retweets, comments, like/dislike on the news related to given subject matter (in this case Hyderabad rape case)

3. To study the outlook of the sample toward violence against women (sexual violence).

4. Study Public sentiment and attitude in regard to Hyderabad rape case. Study correlation to media and demands for tougher punishment. Throughout my literature review process there were enough empirical evidences to establish media exposure generally tends to strengthen tougher punishment rhetoric. Researcher wanted to study if that belief is also true in case of incidents of sexual violence against women.

Hypothesis

There is enough empirical evidence to establish that exposure to media has always resulted in tougher rhetoric around crime and punishment throughout the world

1. Mainstream media plays an important role in formulating public opinion for tougher punishments in reporting violence against women.

2. Mainstream media does not play an important role in formulating public opinion for tougher punishments in reporting violence against women.

Methodology

Primary data was collected through survey and 80 respondents responded to the questionnaire. The sample size was purposely kept diverse in terms of age, income group and educational qualification in order to capture pan India response so that the response could be studied in different strata of the society. Secondary data was collected through books, research papers and online study material.

Result and Findings

80 respondents were studied during the research study. They responded to the various questions asked through questionnaire.

Gender. In the sample 40% respondents were male, 59% respondents were female and 1% didn't prefer to say.

Gender	Number
Male	32
female	47
Prefer not to say	1

Educational Qualification: In the sample 51% respondents were under graduate, 30% were post graduate, 14% were senior secondary students, 8% were high school students and 2% were primary school students.

Educational qualification	Number
Primary	2
High school	3
Senior secondary	12
Under Graduate	44
Post graduate	26

Income Group: In the sample 50% of the people earn less than 2 lakh rupees, 22% people earn between 2-4 lakh, 14% of the people earn between 4-8 lakh, 10% of the people earn between 8-12 lakh and 4% of the people earn more than 12 lakh rupees.

Income per annum	No. of People
2 lakh per annum or less	29
2-4 lakh per annum	13
4-8 lakh per annum	8
8-12 lakh per annum	6
12 lakh per annum or more	2

Age: In the sample 66% respondents were from the age group of 20-30, 15% of the respondents were from age group 20 or under, 10% of the respondents were from age group 40 and above and 9% of the respondents were from age group 30-40.

Age	No. of people
20 or under	12
20-30	53
30-40	7
40 and above	8

Living Settlement: In the sample 60% respondents are from the city population, 21% of the respondents are from the metropolitan population, 13% of the respondent are from the town population and 5% of the respondents are from village population.

Settlement area	No. of people
Metropolitan	17
City	48
Town	10
Village	5

Q1. Do you watch/ read news daily?

As per the response of the respondents 43% of the respondents responded that they mostly watch the news daily, 30% of the respondents responded that they always watch /read news on daily basis , 25% of the respondents responded that they sometimes watch/read news and 2% respondents responded that they rarely watch/read news on daily basis.

Response	No. of people
Always	23
Mostly	33
sometimes	19
Rarely	5

Q2. How many hours do you spend daily watching/reading news?

As per the response of the respondents 30% of the respondents responded that they mostly watch/read the news for one hour on daily basis, 29% of the respondents responded that they watch /read news for half an hour on daily basis, 16% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news for two hours, 14% respondents responded that they watch/read news for less than half an hour and 11% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news on daily basis for more than three hours.

No of hour	No of people
3 hour or more	8
2 hour	11
1 hour	21
half an hour	20
less than half an hour	10

Q3. What's your main source of news consumption?

As per the response of the respondents 46% of the respondents responded that they mostly consume their news from television, 25% of the respondents responded that they consume their news from news apps, 23% of the respondents responded that they consume their news from social media and 6% respondents responded that they consume their news from newspaper.

Source	No of people
Television	37
News apps	20
Social media	18
Newspaper	5

Q4. Which social media app do you use most to read/watch news?

As per the response of the respondents 46% of the respondents responded that they mostly consume their news from television, 25% of the respondents responded that they consume their news from news apps, 23% of the respondents responded that they consume their news from social media and 6% respondents responded that they consume their news from newspaper.

App	No of people
Facebook	21
What's App	10
Instagram	23
Reddit	1
You Tube	25

Q5. How many hours do you spend daily on social media watching/reading news?

As per the response of the respondents 34% of the respondents responded that they mostly watch/read the news on social media for half an hour on daily basis, 22% of the respondents responded that they watch /read news on social media for one hour on daily basis, 19% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news on social media for one and half hours, 14% respondents responded that they watch/read news on social media 2two hour or and 11% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news on social media for less than half an hour.

Time	No of people
less than half an hour	9
half an hour	27
1 hour	18
1 and a half hour	15
2 hour or more	11

Q6. How many hours do you spend regularly watching reading news through conventional (Radio/Television/Newspaper) media?

As per the response of the respondents 26% of the respondents responded that they mostly watch/read the news on traditional media for less than half hour on daily basis, 21% of the respondents responded that they watch /read news on traditional media for one hour on daily basis, 23% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news on traditional media for less than half a hour, 16% respondents responded that they watch/read news on traditional media for one and half hour and 14% of the respondents responded that they watch/read news on traditional media for less than hour.

Time	No of people
less than half an hour	18
half an hour	21
1 hour	17
1 and a half hour	13
2 hour or more	11

Q7. Why do you like a certain news programme?

As per the response of the respondents 79% of the respondents responded that due to content coverage they like a certain programme and 21% responded that due to anchor they like a certain programme.

Reason	No of people
Anchor	16
Content coverage	60

Q8. Which genre of the news you watch the most?

As per the response of the respondents 45% of the respondents responded that they like political news , 24% like news related to crime , 14% like news related to entertainment , 9% like news related to business and 8 % like news related to sports.

Genre	No of people
Politics	36
Crime	19
Entertainment / Page 3	11
Business	7
Sports	6

Q9. Which kind of crime news you are most likely to follow?

As per the response of the respondents 52% of the respondents responded that they follow rape/sexual violence crime news , 26% follow riot/civil disruption news related to crime , 8% follow news related to murder and 3% follow news related to robbery/arson.

Crime	No of people
Rape/ sexual violence	38
Riot / Civil disruptions	19
Murder	6
Fraud / Sec 420	8
Robbery /Arson	2

Q10. What is your general reaction to the news of rape? Sexual violence against women?

As per the response of the respondents 68% of the respondents responded that they feel angry on such news, 26% feel disgust, 4% shock and 2% grief.

Reaction	No of people
Anger	50
Disgust	19
Shock	3
Grief	6

Q11. Do you react (like, dislike) retweet, comment or share news related top sexual violence against women?

As per the response of the respondents 66% of the respondents responded that yes they do react to such news and 34% said that they do not react to such news.

Response	No of people
Yes	58
No	30

Q12. If yes than what is your comment generally about?

As per the response of the respondents 51% of the respondents responded that they demand for safety for women , 31% asking for punishment , 8% express anger, 8% question authority and 2% express grief .

Comment	No of people
Demanding better safety for women	30
Asking for punishment	18
Expressing anger	5
Questioning authority	5
Expressing grief	1

Q13. What was your reaction to Hyderabad rape case incident?

As per the response of the respondents 67% of the respondents responded that they had anger inside, 21% had feeling of disgust, 6% were shocked and 6% had grief.

Reaction	No of people
Anger	53
Disgust	17
Shock	5
Grief	5

Q14. Through which medium you came to know of Hyderabad Rape Case?

As per the response of the respondents 45% of the respondents responded that they came to know through social media, 35% came to know through television, 11% through news app, 5% through newspaper and 4% through social contacts.

Medium	No of people
News paper	4
Social contacts (Family, Friends, Classmates)	3
Social Media	36
Television or Radio	28
News App	9

Q15. Through which medium you followed coverage of Hyderabad rape case?

As per the response of the respondents 40% of the respondents responded that they followed coverage of Hyderabad rape case through social media, 39% followed through television, 15% followed through news app, 5% followed news through social contacts and 1% followed through newspaper.

Medium	No of people
Social Media	33
Television or Radio	32
News App	12
News paper	1
Social contacts (Family, Friends, Classmates)	4

Q16. Did you reacted (like, dislike) retweet, comment or shared news related to encounters of accused of Hyderabad rape case?

As per the response of the respondents 53% of the respondents responded that they did share news or comment on news related to Hyderabad rape case wherein 47% respondents responded that did not share or comment on news related to Hyderabad rape case.

Response	No of people
Yes	42
No	37

Q17. What was your reaction to the encounter "Accused" in Hyderabad rape case?

As per the response of the respondents 70% of the respondents responded that they were satisfied with the encounter (happy), 21% respondents responded that they were appalled by the encounter (angry) and 9% were indifferent to the encounter.

Reaction	No. of people
Satisfied with encounter (Happy)	56
Appalled by encounter (Angry)	17
Indifference to encounter	7

Q18. Do they think the situation, being what it was, it was right for police to fire on accused?

As per the response of the respondents 66% felt that police did the right thing, 23% felt that may be police did the right thing and 11 % felt that it was wrong action of police.

Response	No. of people
Yes	58
Maybe	20
No	10

Q19. If yes, than what was your comment about?

As per the response of the respondents 36% paid their tribute to victim, 34% felt that Telangana police did the right thing, 14% expressed joy, 12% questioned police encounter and 4% applauded Telangana police.

Response	No. of people
Applauding Telangana police	2
Tribute to victim, for ex RIP Disha	20
Questioning police encounter	7
Expressing joy	8
Applauding Telangana government	19

Q20. What according to you should be punishment for rape of a child (below 13yrs)?

As per the response of the respondents 63% demanded for death sentence, 25% demanded castration, 6% demanded life imprisonment, 5% demanded 10 year jail term and 1% demanded 15 year jail term.

Punishment	No of people
Death sentence	50
Castration	20
Life imprisonment	5
15 year of jail term	1
10 year of jail term or less	4

Q21. What according to you should be punishment for rape?

As per the response of the respondents 61% demanded for death sentence, 25% demanded castration, 11% demanded life imprisonment and 3% demanded 10-year jail term.

Punishment	No of people
Death sentence	49
Castration	20
Life imprisonment	9
15 year of jail term	0
10 year of jail term or less	2

Q22. Do you think there should be a chance of prison reform for rape convicts?

As per the response of the respondents 40% responded yes, 36% demanded responded no and 24% responded may be.

Response	No of people
Yes	32
No	29
Maybe	19

Q23. Do you think there should be harder punishment in case of rape/sexual violence?

As per the response of the respondents 95% responded yes and 5% responded no.

Response	No of people
Yes	76
Maybe	4
No	

Q24. Do you think encounter should have been right step even if convicts were not fleeing from scene (According to official statement)?

As per the response of the respondents 51% responded yes, 30% responded maybe and 19% responded no

Response	No of people
Yes	41
Maybe	24
No	15

Q25. What according to you is best solution to stop incidents of sexual violence (rape) against women?

As per the response of the respondents 37% responded that strict implementation of law and order is the best solution, 36% responded capital punishment is the best solution, 14% responded education is the best solution, 11% responded fast track courts are the best solution and 2% responded gender equality is the best solution.

Solution	No of people
Capital punishment (death sentence) for rape	34
Strict implementation of law and order	34
Education	13
Fast track court	10
Gender equality	2

Q26. Who according to you is responsible for incidents of rape?

As per the response of the respondents 32% responded that weak law and order are responsible for incidents of rape, 23% responded rapists are responsible for rape incidents, 21% responded illiteracy is responsible for rape incidents, 14% responded that misogynistic society is responsible for rape incidents and 10% responded that elongated judicial proceedings are responsible for rape incidents.

Response	No of people
Weak law and order	26
Rapists	18
Un-education	17
Misogynistic society (Anti Women dogmas)	11
Elongated judicial proceedings	8

Limitation

The biggest limitation that the researcher faced during conducting this research was that due to the pandemic of Covid-19, the researcher was not able to visit people in person for collecting their response through questionnaire but had to collect the response through online mode. Researcher was not able to approach people in person due to lockdown restrictions and Covid guidelines. In addition, replies could be received from a large number of respondents. Which can yield even better results.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

As per the research conducted, though television is still prominent source of news consumption, it has been given tough competition from news apps and social media. However when you see in depth viewership/ readership behavior it presents different reality. Even though People who watch news on television though make 47% of the sample size, only 51% of them watch news for 1 hour or more while among people who read/view news on new media 55% consume news for more than 1 hour. This difference looks insignificant but keeping in mind the nascent nature of new media it's quite important. It could also be seen that people are more attracted to crime of sexual nature as per the research conducted and While reacting to instances of sexual violence against women, men are more likely to express anger or disgust while women are more saddened and shocked by the event. Reason for following could be that women can sympathize more with the victim while men focus more on crime and criminal rather than victim.

It could be visibly seen through the survey conducted that people followed social media for Hyderabad rape case rather than television or traditional media. This reflects that how new media is making its mark among people and how social media created public opinion regarding Hyderabad rape case encounter. People supported the encounter as they believed that fast track justice should be given in the rape cases in India and they felt encounter was the right way of justice.

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